

UNFCCC SB62 – CREAM REPORT ON THE STATE OF NEGOTIATIONS – FOCUS ON ADAPTATION

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INDEX

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. ADAPTATION: CENTRAL ISSUES AND OUTCOMES	4
1.1. Global Goal On Adaptation (GGA).....	4
1.2. National Adaptation Plans (NAPS)	5
1.3. Adaptation fund	5
2. BROADER NEGOTIATION THEMES.....	6
2.1. Climate finance and the Baku to Belém roadmap	6
2.2. Cross-cutting considerations	6
2.3. Adaptation and synergies with other agendas	7
3. OTHER NEGOTIATION THEMES	7
3.1. Global Stocktake (GST) & UAE Dialogue	7
3.2. Just Transition Work Programme (JTWP).....	7
3.3. Finance and the adaptation fund	8
3.4. Loss and damage – Warsaw International Mechanism (WIM)	8
3.5. Transparency & reporting	8
3.6. Mitigation Work Programme (MWP)	8
3.7. Technology and capacity building.....	8
3.8. Clean Development Mechanism (CDM)	9
3.9. International aviation and maritime emissions	9
3.10. Forum on the impact of response measures	9
3.11. Gender Action Plan (GAP).....	9
3.12. Agriculture and synergies with Rio conventions	9

SUMMARY TABLE OF ALL SB62 AGENDA ITEMS	10
TIMELINE OF KEY DATES LEADING TO COP30	11
COP30 LOGISTICS OVERVIEW	11
Accommodation:	11
Mobility.....	12
Security and health	12
Venue	12
Digital infrastructure	12

UNFCCC SB62

CREAF REPORT ON THE STATE OF NEGOTIATIONS

FOCUS ON ADAPTATION

JUNE 16TH TO 26TH, 2025 – BONN, GERMANY

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The UNFCCC's 62nd Subsidiary Bodies (SB62) sessions in Bonn marked a pivotal moment in the lead-up to COP30 in Belém. Adaptation was a central focus, especially in negotiations on the Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA), National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), and the governance of the Adaptation Fund. Despite some progress in technical frameworks, political divergence, especially around means of implementation and finance—persist. The Global South emphasized equity, finance, and procedural legitimacy, while developed countries focused on streamlining and operational clarity.

1. ADAPTATION: CENTRAL ISSUES AND OUTCOMES

1.1. Global Goal On Adaptation (GGA)

Negotiations centered on finalizing a list of indicators to monitor progress towards the GGA. Parties began with 490 proposed indicators and agreed to narrow these down to **no more than 100**.

- **Key Tensions:**

- The inclusion of indicators related to **means of implementation (MOI)** (e.g., finance, technology transfer) was heavily debated. Developing countries (G77+China, African Group) insisted on their inclusion, while some developed Parties (Australia, Canada) sought to focus on impact and outcome indicators.
- Disagreements on **indicator governance**: Some countries wanted indicators set by Parties, others preferred expert-led decisions. A compromise was proposed, including Party presence in expert discussions at the end of summer (August or September).

- Concerns were raised about **data availability and capacities**, especially in vulnerable countries.
- **Agreed Outcomes:**
 - The expert panel will reduce the list, ensuring global applicability, national flexibility, and inclusion of socio-economic, human rights, and gender consideration.
 - Indicators will distinguish between core (probably globally aggregated) and optional (nationally relevant) types. The debate still remains on how many will be core and how many operational.
 - The negotiation concluded with [draft negotiating texts](#)¹ after a long negotiation (longer than any other topic) and the dispute between the block led by the Arab Group and the block of Western countries led by the European Union and Australia.

1.2. National Adaptation Plans (NAPS)

Negotiations on NAPS were procedural and deadlocked due to disagreements over text framing and structure:

- **Process Dispute:** G77+China demanded line-by-line negotiations to preserve inclusivity; EU and UK preferred section-by-section to expedite progress.
- **Finance-Linked Tensions:** The most contested language related to acknowledging “limited progress” by developing countries due to resource constraints—a framing supported by LDCs but opposed by the EU.
- **Outcome:** A **Conference Room Paper (CRP)**² brought by G77+China, which will serve as the starting point for negotiations at COP30.

1.3. Adaptation fund

The transition of the Adaptation Fund’s governance from the Kyoto Protocol (CMP) to the Paris Agreement (CMA) has raised legal and structural issues:

- **Governance Uncertainty:** Contentious issues include the composition of the Fund’s Board and the appropriate terminology (Annex I vs. developed/developing countries).

¹ UNFCCC (2025). *Draft text on GGA — SBSTA 62 agenda item 5(a) / SBI 62 agenda item 11(a)* (Version 25/06/2025, 23:32) - <https://unfccc.int/documents/648556>.

² Available at https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/CRP_G77_China_proposal_SBI62_i11c_NAPs.pdf

- **Operational Concerns:** There was no consensus on how to transition existing trustee arrangements or ensure continuity in secretariat services.
- **Next Steps:** Two draft texts ([one informal](#)³ and [one from G77+China](#)⁴) will be forwarded to COP30, including proposals for institutional reform and clearer CMA alignment.

2. BROADER NEGOTIATION THEMES

2.1. Climate finance and the Baku to Belém roadmap

The Roadmap aims to mobilize **\$1.3 trillion annually by 2035**, with adaptation as a priority:

- **Challenges Identified:**
 - Heavy reliance on private and institutional finance risks deepening inequities if enabling conditions in recipient countries are not improved.
 - Stakeholders emphasized the need to **bridge local projects to global finance**, especially via risk-reduction tools and asset securitization models.
- **Process Developments:**
 - Consultations at SB62 helped inform the upcoming Belém report, which will detail how this finance should be sourced, structured, and delivered—especially for forests and nature-based solutions (Tropical Forest Forever Facility, COP30 presidency proposal).

2.2. Cross-cutting considerations

Parties debated whether the final GGA indicators and adaptation reports should include references to **social inclusion** (e.g., Indigenous Peoples, gender, youth, Afro-descendant communities):

- **Conflict Lines:** The African Group, Arab Group, and China opposed this paragraph; the EU, Canada, UK, and South American countries insisted it be retained.
- **Negotiation Implications:** The debate revealed ongoing differences in political and cultural framing of vulnerability and adaptation responsibility.

³ Available at https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/G77_and_China_CRP_on_Adaptation_Fund.pdf

⁴ Available at <https://unfccc.int/event/sbi-62>

2.3. Adaptation and synergies with other agendas

- COP30 is expected to produce guidance on aligning **NAPs, NDCs, and biodiversity plans (NBSAPs)** under an integrated framework. This is a priority for COP30 presidency.
- The new initiative supported by Greenpeace **API4Forests (5-Year Forest Action Plan⁵)** may serve as a model for adaptation-mitigation synergy, linking Article 5 (forests) and Article 7 (adaptation) of the Paris Agreement.

3. OTHER NEGOTIATION THEMES

3.1. Global Stocktake (GST) & UAE Dialogue

- The implementation of the GST outcomes was a central procedural issue. Four options for advancing the UAE-facilitated dialogue were proposed: adopt the co-facilitators' morning text, adopt the afternoon revision, consider both, or defer the item entirely.
- Parties remained divided on whether the UAE Dialogue should focus narrowly on climate finance (Article 9.1) or reflect the broader GST outcome dimensions. No consensus was reached, and multiple texts were forwarded for consideration at SB63 and COP30.

3.2. Just Transition Work Programme (JTWP)

- Paragraph 11g of the draft text—regarding the phase-out of fossil fuels—was the key point of contention.
 - **Option 1** includes language on a just, equitable fossil fuel phase-out.
 - **Option 2** focuses on universal access to clean, reliable energy without explicit fossil fuel references.
 - **Option 3** omits the paragraph entirely.
- Bolivia defended fossil fuels for development; Colombia emphasized the climate-security link. The text was forwarded to SB63 in three bracketed options.

⁵ Greenpeace (2025). *COP30 Forest Action Plan* (Discussion Paper). June 2025 - <https://www.greenpeace.org/static/planet4-international-stateless/2025/06/4a3f1b85-cop30-forest-action-plan-proposal.pdf>

3.3. Finance and the adaptation fund

- Discussions on aligning the Adaptation Fund under the Paris Agreement faced continued disagreement on governance (Board composition), legal transitions, and classification terminology (Annex I vs. developed/developing).
- Two texts—an informal co-facilitators' note and a G77+China proposal—were carried forward to SBI63. The decision on whether to merge or proceed with separate texts remains open.

3.4. Loss and damage – Warsaw International Mechanism (WIM)

- Negotiators structured a draft decision for the 2024 WIM review, focusing on strengthening implementation, scaling finance, enhancing technical assistance, and clarifying national planning.
- Disagreement persists around the guidance and scope of national loss-and-damage plans. The decision will be finalized at SB63.

3.5. Transparency & reporting

- SBSTA worked on upgrading the GHG Data Interface and enhancing inventory support tools, with further development planned for SBSTA64.
- The Consultative Group of Experts (CGE) began its mandate renewal process, including discussion of its role, composition, and support functions.
- A territorial dispute over inventory references (Argentina–UK) was noted but not resolved. Broader discussions on capacity building for reporting will continue at SBI63.

3.6. Mitigation Work Programme (MWP)

- Parties debated the usefulness and design of a proposed digital MWP platform.
- Divergence emerged between countries that see the MWP as lacking ambition and others that argue it already functions adequately with current tools.
- A decision text for COP30 is not yet finalized; work will continue at SB63.

3.7. Technology and capacity building

- The Climate Technology Centre's (CTC) review was initiated, but agreement was not reached on host criteria or future scope.

- The Technology Implementation Programme (TIP) was debated, particularly regarding its inclusion of AI, hydrogen, and CCUS. No decision text was adopted.
- Parties discussed linking the Technology Mechanism more closely with the Financial Mechanism (e.g., GEF, GCF). Further discussions were scheduled for SB63.
- Capacity-building frameworks are undergoing review, with gaps in technical training and institutional coordination identified, particularly in least-developed countries.

3.8. Clean Development Mechanism (CDM)

- SBSTA forwarded proposals for the phased termination of the CDM and reallocation of its remaining resources.
- Questions remain over the use of residual CDM funds—possible directions include support to Article 6 mechanisms, adaptation finance, or capacity-building programs.

3.9. International aviation and maritime emissions

- ICAO and IMO presented updates on their climate initiatives. No decisions were taken. The issue was forwarded for further discussion at SBSTA63.

3.10. Forum on the impact of response measures

- Parties reviewed the functions of the Katowice Committee of Experts on the Impacts of the Implementation of Response Measures (KCI).
- Disagreements emerged over the treatment of unilateral trade measures. A global dialogue proposal is under development for further review at SB63.

3.11. Gender Action Plan (GAP)

- Technical workshops explored strengthening the GAP, focusing on intersectionality, Indigenous women's rights, and data disaggregation.
- Some Parties resisted the inclusion of "gender-diverse" language. The updated GAP text remains under negotiation, with final approval expected later this year.

3.12. Agriculture and synergies with Rio conventions

- SBSTA advanced work on the joint agriculture and food systems workstream, with new emphasis on synthesizing workshop outputs and creating a centralized data portal.

- A separate track addressed coordination between the UNFCCC, CBD, and UNCCD. Although many Parties expressed support, concrete text on synergies is yet to be developed.

SUMMARY TABLE OF ALL SB62 AGENDA ITEMS

TOPIC	OUTCOME AT SB62	Next Step
Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA)	Agreed to reduce 490 indicators to ≤100, with core and context-specific sub-indicators	Expert review (Aug 2025), COP30
National Adaptation Plans (NAPs)	No consensus on draft structure or negotiation modality; CRP from G77+China forwarded	COP30 (SB63)
Adaptation Fund Governance	Governance reform deferred; two texts (co-facilitators & G77+China) advanced	SBI63 & COP30
Baku Adaptation Roadmap (BAR)	Divergent views; no common framework for transformational adaptation adopted	To be revisited at COP30
Adaptation Committee Review	No agreement on COP vs. CMA roles; decision postponed	SB70
GST & UAE Dialogue	No consensus on process/text; texts bracketed and carried forward	SB63 & COP30
Just Transition Work Programme (JTWP)	Text stuck on fossil fuel language; three options forwarded	SB63
Loss & Damage – WIM Review	Draft structured; finance and planning guidance unresolved	SB63
Transparency & Reporting (CGE, GHG Interface)	GHG tools progressed; CGE renewal discussed; reporting support debated	SB63 & SBSTA64
Mitigation Work Programme (MWP)	Platform debated; ambition vs. capacity gap unresolved	SB63
Technology & TIP	No agreement on scope; emerging sectors and finance linkages discussed	SBI63
Capacity Building	Fifth review underway; highlighted gaps in institutional support	SBI63
Clean Development Mechanism (CDM)	Sunset proposals forwarded; fund reallocation unresolved	CMP20
Aviation & Shipping Emissions	ICAO/IMO updates presented; technical talks delayed	SBSTA63
Response Measures Forum	Trade measures disputed; global dialogue proposed	SB63

Gender Action Plan (GAP)	Workshops advanced; text stalled on inclusive language	Further negotiation (2025)
Agriculture & Rio Synergies	Work on agriculture synthesis and inter-convention synergies ongoing	SBSTA63

TIMELINE OF KEY DATES LEADING TO COP30

- August 2025: Final list of GGA indicators to be prepared
- BRICS meeting in Russia September
- October 2025: World Bank/IMF Annual Meetings – potential finance announcements
- November 2025: COP30, Belém

COP30 LOGISTICS OVERVIEW

Accommodation:

- **Short-Term Rentals** will be the primary lodging option available during COP30.
- A **centralized accommodation platform**, the same used for COP29 (Baku), will launch at the **end of July 2025**. It will include:
 - Listings for short-term rentals (mostly arranged with local state agents) and ships (MSC and Costa).
 - Pricing with all ranges, for ships the prices will start at 700€ per night (only chambers of 2) but no **cancellation policies**.
- **Over 29,000 rooms and 55,000 beds** are expected to be made available.
- Additional accommodation (hotels and apartments) are being **built** and will be completed **before October 2025**.
- **Ships** docked within a 1-hour range from the venue will serve as hotel alternatives, with dedicated shuttle services at certain points.
- **All hotels will be booked by delegations (not a lot of availability)**

Mobility

- **Public transportation** will connect the venue to hotels, city center, and tourist areas.
- **Dedicated COP lanes** are being created, ensuring a **30–35 minute commute** between most accommodations and the venue.
- **Boat transport** options will be included for those staying on ships.

Security and health

- **Multi-agency coordination** to guarantee a secure environment.
- The COP30 venue will be located in one of the **most secure areas of the city**.
- Attendees will have **free access** to Brazil's public healthcare system (SUS).
- **Vaccinations** recommended: **yellow fever and measles** (non-mandatory, precautionary only).

Venue

- Located in a **500,000 m² park**, formerly an airport, now redeveloped for COP30.
- **Green Zone** and **Blue Zone** will be nearly integrated, promoting better interaction.
- The venue will be composed of **temporary, sustainable structures**.
- Will be certified **carbon neutral (PAS 2060)**.
- Other locations in the city will be used as hubs for side events by specific organizations.

Digital infrastructure

- A **central online platform** will manage accommodation, logistics updates, side events, and official documentation.
- Managed jointly by the Brazilian government and the UNFCCC Secretariat.